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RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SALEM****FIRST NAME: MOHAMMAD****PROGRAM CODE: DIRGD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

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QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-410D

1. What are the four main components of dissertation research typically prepared by students?
- Abstract, Introduction, Methods, Results
- Literature Review, Methodology, Data Analysis, Conclusion
- Dissertation concept paper, Dissertation prospectus, Dissertation, Dissertation manuscript¹**
- Research question, Hypothesis, Data collection, Discussion

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

2. Which of the following is not one of the elements typically included in a quantitative research question?

- Variables
- Participant characteristics
- Setting
- Researcher's background²**

3. Which of the following is a key factor in judging research questions and narrowing content or method gaps in the literature?

- Length of the question
- Number of variables involved
- Social significance and feasibility³**
- Complexity of statistical analysis

4. What are the two primary duties of a researcher?

- To be creative and original
- To get the facts right and cite sources⁴**
- To write lengthy papers and use complex language
- To challenge authority and reject established knowledge

² Ibid., 28–29.

³ Ibid., 29.

⁴ [Kate L. Turabian](#), *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition, (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139.

5. When evaluating your research questions, what should you look for?

- Questions with obvious answers
- Questions that reinforce existing beliefs
- Questions whose answers might lead to new ways of thinking⁵**
- Questions that are easy to research

6. What is the relationship between plagiarism and intention?

- Plagiarism only occurs with intentional copying
- Unintentional copying is not plagiarism
- Plagiarism is a perceived act, not just an intended one⁶**
- Intention is the only factor in determining plagiarism

7. When writing the conclusion of an essay, what should you avoid?

- Restating your answer to the question
- Summarizing the main points
- Including a final, broad statement
- Introducing new information or ideas⁷**

8. How should the presentation of a theory be guided in a paper?

- By providing a comprehensive overview

⁵ Ibid., 27–28.

⁶ Ibid., 80.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition, (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 10.

- By the particular problems that animate your paper
- By summarizing all aspects equally⁸**
- By focusing on the historical context

9. What is the recommended approach for presenting the "Introduction" section in the Dissertation Concept Paper?

- A detailed analysis of each literature element
- A one-paragraph summary of each element of the literature⁹**
- A series of bullet points highlighting key concepts
- An extensive literature review covering all related topics

10. For doctoral students with less research experience, it is recommended that they?

- Conducting a pilot study
- Focusing solely on qualitative research
- Using a structured approach to develop a schema for understanding dissertation research¹⁰**

Choosing Simpler Research Questions

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⁸ Ibid., 13.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 28.

¹⁰ Ibid., 20.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.